

ADAPTIVE PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AS A MODEL IN ACHIEVING CAREER SUCCESS

WITA FARLA^{1*}, BADIA PERIZADE², ZUNAIDAH³ and ISNI ANDRIANA⁴

^{1*} Ph.D Student of Doctoral School of Management, Faculty of Economics, Universitas Sriwijaya, Indonesia.
Correspondent Email: witaFarla@unsri.ac.id

^{2,3,4} Faculty of Economics, Universitas Sriwijaya, Indonesia.

Email: badiaperizade@fe.unsri.ac.id², zunaidah@fe.unsri.ac.id³, isniandriana@fe.unsri.ac.id⁴

Abstract

This research aims to develop, analyze, and test an empirical model of the effect of self-reflection on career success through adaptive professional development as a mediating variable. The population in this study were lecturers at five public universities in the region of South Sumatra, Indonesia. Samples were taken proportionally at each university. The data used in this study is primary data collected by using questionnaires. The collected is then analyzed using the Structural Equation Models (SEM) analysis technique. The results showed that self-reflection affects adaptive professional development and career success, then adaptive professional development affects career success and mediates the influence between self-reflection and career success. This research concludes that adaptive professional development can act as a mediating variable between self-reflection and career success.

Keywords: self-reflection, adaptive professional development, career success

Introduction

During the last two decades, the concept of career success has become one of the most widely discussed topics in career management studies which are part of Human Resource Management (Santos, 2016). The definition of career success has evolved. This is caused by the influence of several factors, both internal and external factors from individuals and organizations. The definition of career success has evolved from a traditional definition to a modern definition. According to the traditional definition of career success is measured based on the development of the individual hierarchy or the sequence of promotions to achieve positions in the organization while the modern definition includes psychological elements of how individuals view career success (Rasdi et al., 2009). Career success is the accumulation of achievements during one's work experience (Haines, Hamouche & Saba, 2014; Poon, et al., 2015). Career success can also be said as a result of one's experience and is an accumulation of real or perceived achievements (Dai & Song, 2016). Career success is not only determined by the organization but is managed by the individual himself. Individuals will be responsible for managing and continually finding their careers taking into account the changes that occur around them (Zamir, 2018).

Apart from employees, career success also needs to be achieved by a lecturer. Lecturers are one of the human resources in universities. In Indonesia, there is an increase in the number of lecturers in 2017-2020. The lecturers are spread in various universities, both public universities and private universities. The number of lecturers in 2018 increased by 19.23 percent from 2017.

In 2019 the number of lecturers in Indonesia increased by 4.68 percent from 2018 and in 2020 the number of lecturers in Indonesia increased by 1.39 percent from 2019 (source: Higher Education Statistics, 2017-2020). The same thing happened to five state universities in South Sumatra, Indonesia. At these five universities, the number of lecturers also increased along with the increase in the number of lecturers in Indonesia. The data shows that this profession in Indonesia is quite attractive due to the increase in the number of lecturers in Indonesia.

When carrying out his professional duties, a lecturer must carry out educational, research, and community service activities. Thus, the profession of a lecturer has relatively many tasks (Rubiono & Finahari, 2017). On the other hand, the profession of a lecturer is quite attractive where there is an increase in the number of lecturers in Indonesia from year to year. One of the most wanted achievements is the academic position as a professor (Ramli et al., 2016) because this is related to improving the academic career of lecturers (Santos, 2016). Professor is a lecturer's highest academic position. Although there is an increase in the number of lecturers, the number of lecturers who have academic positions as professors are still small. This also happened to five state universities in South Sumatra. In 2020, the number of professors at these five universities did not reach 20 percent. Ministry of Education and Culture Republic of Indonesia said that the number of professors at universities in Indonesia should ideally be 20 percent of the total number of lecturers at these universities.

The low number of professors can be caused by the difficulty of the requirements. The research of Fitriana et al. (2016) stated that one of the causes of the difficulty of lecturers achieving professorships is that they must have publications in reputable international journals. This is in line with Sutherland (2017) who states that to achieve a professorship academic position, a lecturer must have scientific publications. The small number of lecturers who become professors demand lecturers to evaluate their academic experiences and develop plans related to academic career achievements. Thus, lecturers need to do self-reflection to achieve career success.

Obligations and work requirements as well as changes in policies related to lecturers' careers demand lecturers to always adapt to challenges and changes in their work environment. This study adopted the Career Construction Theory by Savickas. This theory explains the demand to always adapt to the work environment in developing a career (Xie et al., 2016). One of them is self-reflection. Career Construction Theory discusses the concept of self-reflection for individuals (Savickas, 2016). Self-reflection is the ability to assess personal experience, increase understanding, self-growth, and develop professionalism in a career (Caux & et al., 2017). Self-reflection can also be characterized by openness to experience (Kim & Shin, 2020).

Several previous studies have examined the effect of self-reflection on career success. The research of Hakhmigari et al. (2019), Kayasheva & Khanova (2019), and Anseel (2017) found that reflection activities have a significant effect on individual career success, but the results of the study of Kuijpers et al. (2006) prove the opposite where self-reflection does not affect one's career success. Seggelen & Dam's research (2016) also found that reflection does not affect individual job satisfaction which is one indicator of career success. The results of this study indicate that there is still a research gap so to fill this gap, this study will add an adaptive

professional development variable. Adaptive professional development will act as a mediating variable between self-reflection and career success.

One type of professional development is skill development which aims to increase knowledge and expertise (Romijn et al., 2021). Skill development is an adaptive response to overcome changes in the career environment (Pajic et al., 2018). Thus, professional development carried out by lecturers is adaptive or also called adaptive professional development. Adaptive refers to how individuals face or respond to changes and demands in life and is a behaviour (Dixon, 2007). Adaptive professional development aims to improve the quality of a lecturer's teaching and research (Duță, 2012; Ziedonis & Ahn, 2019) so that it will have an impact on the professional life of lecturers such as success in teaching, job satisfaction, and acknowledgement from colleagues and leaders (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019).

Adaptive professional development for lecturers is considered important because lecturers can maximize their efforts to achieve career success by continuing to carry out adaptive professional development following their field of work. In this study, adaptive professional development is used as a mediating variable between self-reflection and career success. Thus, this study will develop an empirical model by incorporating the concepts of self-reflection and adaptive professional development as instruments for achieving career success.

Literature Review

Career Construction Theory

Career Construction Theory stated by Savickas states that in developing his career one must always adapt to the environment (Xie et al., 2016). The word adaptation has the meaning of changing or matching. When the work environment changes, individuals adapt it to suit their work environment. This theory also applies self-concept in social roles that focus on adapting to a series of transitions from one job to another (Le et al., 2019), or in other words, this theory emphasizes the need for continuous adjustment and development and implementation of self-concept in all areas. Task level to achieve success and job satisfaction. But on the other hand, there are differences in the self-concept of each individual so individuals need to use and improve their competencies (Karatepe & Olugbade, 2017).

Career Construction Theory developed an adaptation model consisting of four processes, namely adaptivity, adaptability resources, adapting responses and adaptation results (Tokar et al., 2019; Xie, et al., 2016). First, adaptivity is indicated by flexibility and willingness to adapt. adaptivity is operationalized through proactive personality (Gao et al., 2019), self-awareness (Pajic et al., 2018), and self-evaluation (Hirschi et al., 2015). In adaptivity, individuals make proactive efforts to cope with changes in the work environment and have specific personalities such as being open to experience (Tokar et al., 2019). Openness to experience can be characterized by activities for self-reflection. This reflection is done consciously on the experiences that have occurred and the current situation. Individuals need to reassess what has been done to set goals in their careers (Savickas, 2013). Second, adaptability resources, which are psychological forces in coping with environmental changes. Adaptability resources are also

called career adaptability. Career adaptability is an individual's ability to adapt to different work environments. Career adaptability contributes to developing and determining individual strategies for managing career tasks and challenges (Le et al., 2019). Career adaptability includes resources owned by individuals such as attitudes, competencies, and behaviours used by employees to match themselves with their careers or jobs (Haibo et.al, 2018).

Third, adaptive responses are shown by adaptive behaviours to changes in the work environment such as career planning, career exploitation (Hirschi et al., 2015), and proactive skill development (Pajic et al., 2018). One indicator of adaptive responses is an increase in the level of competence possessed by individuals (Tokar et al., 2019). In this process, individuals can improve their self-competence by carrying out professional development. Each individual must carry out self-development as a result of environmental changes. Fourth, adaptation results can be in the form of success, goal achievement, and satisfaction (Tokar et al., 2019). Success in a career consists of two forms, namely objective career success or extrinsic career success and subjective career success or intrinsic career success (Chughtai, 2018; Hennekam, 2016; Tharmaseelan et al., 2010). Career Construction Theory aims to explain how people relate their self-concept about work to their work role during their career. Based on the concept of career formation, successful career development is a continuous process of adaptation resulting from the integration of personal needs with social expectations. In addition, this theory also focuses on a person's dynamic process to see work experiences that have been experienced during the career formation process (Rudolph et al., 2019).

Self-Reflection and Adaptive Professional Development

Self-reflection is a self-evaluation activity that refers to a person's personality, actions, thoughts, feelings, and attitudes (Porubčanová & Sejutová, 2020). Reflection activities are activities to look at past experiences (Namaganda, 2020) and emphasize one's knowledge, experience, and emotions as objects of reflection. Career self-reflection is an activity to see the experiences that have been passed during a career. Self-reflection is also a tool to improve self-learning (Anseel, 2017; Meijers & Kuijpers, 2014). Self-reflection will contribute to the process of self-development (Yun et al., 2020), and professional development (Porubčanová & Sejutová, 2020), and is necessary for carrying out continuous professional development (Drude et al., 2019). Based on the description above, the hypothesis is made as follows.

H1. Self-reflection influences adaptive professional development.

Self-Reflection and Career Success

Self-reflection is an activity of observing life experiences as part of the process of self-discovery (Yun et al., 2020). Self-reflection on a career is an activity to reflect on the capacity or ability of a person concerning a career. Career self-reflection is carried out consciously based on the experiences that have been obtained or felt during a career. Through self-reflection, individuals can find out their strengths and weaknesses so that they can achieve professional success and build a career in a sustainable manner (Kayasheva & Khanova, 2019; Anseel, 2017). Career success is a positive accumulation of work and psychological results from one's work experience (Gu & Su, 2016). Self-reflection activities have a relationship with career

success (Kalfon Hakhmigari et al., 2019). Based on the description above, the hypothesis is made as follows.

H2. Self-reflection affects career success

Adaptive Professional Development and Career Success

Adaptive professional development aims for individuals to be able to add skills that are following the demands of the job. Professional development can be done in various ways (Bailey, 2015) including training, formal education, and further professional learning (Hilty et al., 2019). Professional development is useful for increasing professional knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Namaganda, 2020). Through professional development, a person is expected to become more professional (Eldor, 2017). Individuals who carry out professional development will get success in work and job satisfaction (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019; Eddy et al., 2015). Based on the description above, the hypothesis is made as follows.

H3. Adaptive professional development affects career success

Self-Reflection, Career Success, and the Role of Adaptive Professional Development Mediation

Self-reflection is a self-evaluation activity that refers to a person's personality, actions, thoughts, feelings, and attitudes (Porubčanová & Sejutová, 2020). Self-reflection will contribute to the process of self-development (Yun et al., 2020), and professional development (Porubčanová & Sejutová, 2020), and is necessary for carrying out continuous professional development (Drude et al., 2019). Individuals can carry out professional development by identifying the need for learning and exploring their strengths and weaknesses related to the work environment (Eddy et al., 2015). Several studies reveal that professional development requires skills for self-reflection (Drude et al., 2019; Sprott, 2019; Duță, 2012). Professional development is useful for increasing professional knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Namaganda, 2020). Through professional development, a person is expected to become more professional (Eldor, 2017). Individuals who carry out professional development will get success in work and job satisfaction (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019; Eddy et al., 2015). Based on this description, the hypothesis is made as follows.

H4. Adaptive professional development mediates the influence between self-reflection and career success

Based on the description above, the conceptual framework in this study can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methodology

This is quantitative research that will analyze the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable by adding a mediating variable. The independent variable in this study is self-reflection and the dependent variable is career success. The mediating variable in this study is adaptive professional development. The data used in this study is primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The questions in the questionnaire refer to the research indicators. These indicators will be measured using a semantic scale. The research sample consisted of 303 lecturers from five public universities in South Sumatera, Indonesia which were divided proportionally per university. The sample that has been divided proportionally is then drawn again using a random technique at each university.

Result

The target number of respondents in this study was 303 but the actual number of questionnaires filled out by respondents was 292 because there were questionnaires that the respondents did not fill out. The data collected is then processed through several stages of data screening. Data screening consists of three stages, namely missing data checking, outliers checking, and normality testing. Based on the results of data screening, 10 data are considered not good, so these 10 data will be deleted. Thus, the number of data that was originally 292 data turned into 282 data.

Respondent profile

The respondent's profile describes the composition of respondents based on gender, age, academic position, and tenure. The composition can be seen in the following table.

Table 1. Respondent Profile

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender:		
Male	136	48.2
Female	146	51.8
Total	282	100
Age:		
<40 year old	44	15.6
40 – 50 year old	123	43.6
51 – 60 year old	88	31.2
> 60 year old	27	9.6
Total	282	100
Academic position:		
Assistant	27	9.6
Assistant Professor	131	46.4
Associate Professor	124	44.0
Total	282	100
Tenure:		
<10 year	24	8.5
10 – 20 year	113	40.1
21 – 30 year	81	28.7
> 30 year	64	22.7
Total	282	100

Observed based on gender, respondents in this study had almost the same proportion between men and women. Male respondents were 48.2 percent while female respondents were 51.8 percent. Most of the respondents were in the age group of 40 to 50 years as much as 43.6 percent. The second largest age group was 51 to 60 years as much as 31.2 percent. The age group of fewer than 40 years was 15.6 percent and the age group of more than 60 years was 9.6 percent. Most of the respondents are in the academic positions of Assistant Professor and Associate Professor. Assistant Professors are 46.4 percent and Associate Professors are 44 percent. Meanwhile, there are also respondents with the academic position of Assistant as much as 9.6 percent. Observed based on tenure, most of the respondents were in the group of 10 to 20 years of tenure, as many as 40.1 percent, while respondents with 21 to 30 years of tenure and more than 30 years were 28.7 percent and 22.7 percent. Respondents with less than 10 years of tenure were only 8.5 percent.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

In Confirmatory Factor Analysis, validity and reliability tests are carried out on the indicators. Validity and reliability are indicated by the value of loading factor, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The following table shows the results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis.

Table 2: Loading Factor, Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	CR	AVE
Self-reflection	RD1	0.835	0.742	0.590
	RD2	0.927		
	RD3	0.765		
	RD4	0.847		
	RD5	0.945		
	RD6	0.9		
Adaptive professional development	PPA1	0.631	0.941	0.842
	PPA2	0.528		
	PPA4	0.73		
	PPA5	0.836		
	PPA6	0.714		
	PPA7	0.752		
	PPA8	0.705		
	PPA9	0.645		
	Career success	SK2		
SK3		0.534		
SK4		0.602		
SK5		0.648		
SK6		0.559		

Based on the results in table 2, the loading factor value of all indicators is greater than 0.5, the AVE value is above 0.5, and the CR value is greater than 0.7. Thus, validity and reliability are accepted.

Goodness of Fit Model

Goodness of Fit is carried out to see whether a model is good or not. Before the overall Goodness of Fit test is carried out, the Goodness of Fit test is first carried out on each variable and its indicators. As a result, three indicators were discarded, namely RD3, PPA6, and PPA8. Furthermore, the overall Goodness of Fit test was carried out. Here are the results of the Goodness of Fit of the model.

Table 3. Goodness of Fit Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Limit Value	Result	Model Evaluation
Chi-Square (X^2)	Almost 0	285,794	Fit
Probability	$\geq 0,05$	0,059	Fit
CMIN/DF	$\leq 2,00$	1,143	Fit
RMSEA	$\leq 0,08$	0,023	Fit
GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,927	Fit
AGFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,905	Fit
TLI	$\geq 0,95$	0,987	Fit
CFI	$\geq 0,95$	0,989	Fit

Based on the results in table 3, the model is considered fit. This can be seen from all index values that have reached the limit value. As seen in the figure of fit model below.

Figure 2. Fit Model

Structural Model

After the model is declared fit, the next step is to analyze the structural model. Here is the result of the structural model analysis.

Table 4. Standardized Regression Weights

			Estimate
Adaptive professional development	<---	Self-reflection	0.12
Career success	<---	Adaptive professional development	0.864
Career success	<---	Self-reflection	0.262

Based on the results in table 4, the effect of self-reflection on adaptive professional development is 0.12, the effect of adaptive professional development on career success is 0.864, and the effect of self-reflection on career success development is 0.262. After analyzing the structural model, the next step is testing the hypothesis. Hypothesis test results can be seen from the value of Critical Ratio (C.R) and probability value (p-value). The following are the results of hypothesis testing.

Table 5. Regression Weights

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Adaptive professional development	<---	Self-reflection	0,059	0,019	3,087	**
Career success	<---	Adaptive professional development	0,842	0,065	12,961	***
Career success	<---	Self-reflection	0,125	0,021	5,923	***

*** Significant < 0,001

** Significant < 0, 01

The results of the hypothesis test show that all C.R values are greater than 1.96 and the probability values show a significant sign. This means that self-reflection has an effect on adaptive professional development and career success, and also adaptive professional development affects career success. Thus, the first hypothesis H1, the second hypothesis H2, and the third hypothesis H3 can be accepted.

Mediation Test

Mediation test using bootstrapping technique. Hypothesis testing with bootstrapping technique is to check the confidence interval. The bootstrapping technique gives the lower and upper values of the confidence level. Following are the results of the mediating test of the effect of self-reflection on career success mediated by adaptive professional development.

Table 6. Mediation Test

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Status
A x B	0,05	0,02	0,087	0,001	Significant

The results in table 6 show a probability value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 and the lower and upper values do not contain zero values. This means that adaptive professional development mediates the influence between self-reflection and career success. Thus, the fourth hypothesis H4 can be accepted.

Discussion

The Effect of Self-Reflection on Adaptive Professional Development

Hypothesis testing found that self-reflection affects adaptive professional development. Based on Career Construction Theory, self-reflection activities are part of adaptivity. Adaptivity is indicated by flexibility, willingness to adapt, self-awareness (Pajic et al., 2018), and self-evaluation (Hirschi et al., 2015). Individuals who have self-awareness and self-evaluation will be better prepared to face upcoming tasks and are responsible for their professional development (Pajic et al., 2018). In adaptivity, individuals make efforts to cope with changes in the work environment and have specific personalities such as openness to experience (Tokar et al., 2019).

This openness to experience can be likened to activities for self-reflection. Thus, lecturers who can do self-reflection will always evaluate or introspect themselves by assessing their strengths and weaknesses. Based on the results of this introspection, especially on self-weaknesses, a lecturer will try to learn and improve his knowledge and competencies. In the end, these activities are part of adaptive professional development because they are related to the lecturer's self-development as a result of the demands of the work environment.

The Effect of Self-Reflection on Career Success

Hypothesis testing shows that self-reflection affects career success. Self-reflection is part of the adaptation model of Career Construction Theory, namely adaptivity. According to this theory, adaptivity is operationalized by a proactive personality. Individuals with a proactive personality will like planning to achieve success (Pajic et al., 2018) and make proactive efforts to cope with changes that occur in the work environment (Tokar et al., 2019).

Self-reflection is an important skill in many professions. Individuals must learn to self-reflect and self-evaluate to understand feedback on work and to find out whether the work done has fulfilled the standards (Miller & Konstantinou, 2021). If a lecturer has received feedback and knows the standards in his work, then the lecturer will try to do his job better. Thus, through self-reflection, lecturers can develop skills and exploit themselves to achieve career success.

Effect of Adaptive Professional Development on Career Success

Hypothesis testing indicates that adaptive professional development affects career success. Career Construction Theory states that responses to adaptation in work are shown by adaptive behaviours to changes in the work environment. Adaptive behaviours to changes in the work environment are demonstrated by carrying out career planning, career exploitation (Hirschi et al., 2015), and proactive skill development (Pajic et al., 2018).

Proactive skill development is part of adaptive professional development. Through skill development, lecturers can improve their professionalism. Individuals who carry out professional development will get success in work and job satisfaction (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019; Eddy et al., 2015). Richter et al. (2019) in their research states that individuals will carry out professional development because it will be related to promotions. Success in work, job satisfaction, and promotion are some forms of career success.

Adaptive Professional Development Mediates the Influence between Self-Reflection and Career Success

Hypothesis testing found that adaptive professional development mediates the influence between self-reflection and career success. Career Construction Theory states that one of the approaches used by individuals in building their careers is through a personal approach (Savickas, 2005; 2013). In the personal approach, individuals build their careers using self-concepts and individuals are expected to be able to carry out self-reflection activities by referring to experiences that have been received during work. Self-reflection will make individuals reorganize their knowledge and recognize self-weaknesses that require further development (Son, 2018).

Individuals who actively carry out self-reflection will be able to set career goals and identify skills and figure out how these skills can be developed. Through skills identification, individuals can find out what skills they have and do not have. Thus, adaptive professional development activities are needed. Several studies state that individuals who undertake professional development will find success in their work (Cirocki & Farrell, 2019; Eddy et al., 2015). Thus, lecturers who can carry out self-reflection to find out their capacities will carry out adaptive professional development to improve their abilities and eventually, through these abilities and capacities, lecturers will achieve career success.

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion of the research, it can be concluded that self-reflection affects adaptive professional development and career success. Adaptive professional development influences career success and also mediates the influence between self-reflection and career success. Based on these conclusions, it is suggested that the understanding of self-reflection and adaptive professional development needs to be improved so that lecturers can develop career-related plans to achieve career success. Activities related to adaptive professional development need to be improved in the form of training activities that can improve lecturers' competence as well as activities that can support lecturers' expertise such as training that provides certification in certain areas of expertise according to educational background. The limitation of this research is that it only analyzes the concept of a lecturer's career success based on an individual approach. The next research can expand the analysis based on organizational approaches such as institutional support and chief support.

References

- Anseel, F. (2017). Agile learning strategies for sustainable careers: a review and integrated model of feedback-seeking behavior and reflection. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 28, 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2017.07.001>
- Bailey, M. (2015). Professional Development of HR Practitioners – a Phenomenographic Study. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 39(3), 407–429. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-10-2015-0077>
- Caux, C. de, & et al. (2017). Reflection for Learning in Doctoral Training: Writing Groups, Academic Writing Proficiency and Reflective Practice. *Reflective Practice*, 18(4), 463–473.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14623943.2017.1307725>

Chughtai, A. (2018). Authentic leadership, career self-efficacy and career success: a cross-sectional study. *Career Development International*, 23(6–7), 595–607. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-05-2018-0160>

Cirocki, A., & Farrell, T. S. C. (2019). Professional Development of Secondary School EFL Teachers: Voices from Indonesia. *System*, 85, 102111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.102111>

Dai, L., & Song, F. (2016). Subjective Career Success: A Literature Review and Prospect. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 04(03), 238–242. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jhrss.2016.43026>

Dixon, D. R. (2007). Adaptive Behavior Scales. In *International Review of Research in Mental Retardation* (Vol. 34, Issue 07). Elsevier Masson SAS. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0074-7750\(07\)34003-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0074-7750(07)34003-2)

Drude, K. P., Maheu, M., & Hilty, D. M. (2019). Continuing Professional Development: Reflections on a Lifelong Learning Process. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 42(3), 447–461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psc.2019.05.002>

Duță, N. V. (2012). Professional Development of the University Teacher -Inventory of Methods Necessary for Continuing Training. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 33, 1003–1007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.01.273>

Eddy, A., Eddy, D., & Doughty, J. (2015). Evidencing Continual Professional Development: Maximising Impact and Informing Career Planning. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 46(4), 361–364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmir.2015.07.006>

Eldor, L. (2017). The Relationship Between Perceptions of Learning Climate and Employee Innovative Behavior and Proficiency.

Fitriana, A., Satori, D., & Nurdin, D. (2016). Capacity Building of Associate Professors for Improving Lecturers' Performance: A Case Study in a Leading University in Indonesia. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 14, 106–111. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icemal-16.2016.23>

Gao, X., Xin, X., Zhou, W., & Jepsen, D. M. (2019). Combine your “Will” and “Able”: Career adaptability's influence on performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9(JAN), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02695>

Gu, Q., & Su, Y. (2016). How Does Objective Career Success Affect Subjective Career Success? The Moderating Role of Self-Awareness. *Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies*, 04(03), 227–237. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jhrss.2016.43025>

Haibo, Y., Xiaoyu, G., Xiaoming, Z., & Zhijin, H. (2018). Career Adaptability With or Without Career Identity: How Career Adaptability Leads to Organizational Success and Individual Career Success? *Journal of Career Assessment*, 26(4), 717–731. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1069072717727454>

Haines, V. Y., Hamouche, S., & Saba, T. (2014). Career success: Fit or marketability? *Career Development International*, 19(7), 779–793. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-02-2014-0023>

Hennekam, S. (2016). Competencies of Older Workers and Its Influence on Career Success and Job Satisfaction. *Employee Relations: The International Journal*, 38(2).

Hilty, D. M., Liu, H. Y., Stubbe, D., & Teshima, J. (2019). Defining Professional Development in Medicine, Psychiatry, and Allied Fields. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 42(3), 337–356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psc.2019.04.001>

Hirschi, A., Herrmann, A., & Keller, A. C. (2015). Career adaptivity, adaptability, and adapting: A conceptual and empirical investigation. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 87, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.11.008>

Kalfon Hakhmigari, M., Michaeli, Y., J. Dickson, D., Scharf, M., & Shulman, S. (2019). Personality maturation among emerging adults and future career success. *Career Development International*, 24(2), 146–162.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-03-2018-0067>

Karatepe, O. M., & Olugbade, O. A. (2017). The effects of work social support and career adaptability on career satisfaction and turnover intentions. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 23(3), 337–355. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2016.12>

Kayasheva, O. I., & Khanova, Z. G. (2019). The Role of Psychology Students' Reflexivity in Securing Professional Success. *EurAsian Journal of BioSciences*, 13(2), 2051–2056.

Kim, J. H., & Shin, H. S. (2020). Effects of self-reflection-focused career course on career search efficacy, career maturity, and career adaptability in nursing students: A mixed methods study. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 36(5), 395–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.profnurs.2020.03.003>

Kuijpers, M. A. C. T., Schyns, B., & Scheerens, J. (2006). Career competencies for career success. *Career Development Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2161-0045.2006.tb00011.x>

Le, K. K., Hamzah, S. R., & Omar, Z. (2019). Conceptualising Personal Resources on Career Adaptability. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(9), 875–887. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9-i9/6378>

Meijers, F., & Kuijpers, M. (2014). Career learning and career learning environment in Dutch higher education. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 6(2), 295–313. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-06-2013-0025>

Miller, E., & Konstantinou, I. (2021). Using Reflective, Authentic Assessments to Embed Employability Skills in Higher Education. *Journal of Work-Applied Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jwam-02-2021-0014>

Namaganda, A. (2020). Continuing Professional Development as Transformational Learning: A Case Study. *Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(3), 102152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2020.102152>

Pajic, S., Keszler, Á., & Kismihok, G. (2018). Antecedents and outcomes of Hungarian nurses' career adaptability. *International Journal of Manpower*, 34(1), 1–5.

Poon, J. M. L., Briscoe, J. P., Abdul-Ghani, R., & Jones, E. A. (2015). Meaning and determinants of career success: A Malaysian perspective. *Revista de Psicologia Del Trabajo y de Las Organizaciones*, 31(1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rpto.2015.02.002>

Porubčanová, D., & Sejutová, M. (2020). Self-reflection and teacher. *R&E Source. Online Journal for Research and Education*, 18, 113–116.

Ramli, H. S. B., Chin, A. L. L., & Choo, A. C. P. (2016). Career success for women in higher education institution: The factors influencing the success of women academician. *International Business Management*, 10(17), 3929–3935.

Rasdi, R. M., Ismail, M., Uli, J., & Noah, S. M. (2009). Towards developing a theoretical framework for measuring public sector managers' career success. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 33(3), 232–254. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590910950596>

Richter, D., Kleinknecht, M., & Gröschner, A. (2019). What Motivates Teachers to Participate in Professional Development? An Empirical Investigation of Motivational Orientations and the Uptake of Formal Learning Opportunities. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 86, 102929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.102929>

Romijn, B. R., Slot, P. L., & Leseman, P. P. M. (2021). Increasing teachers' intercultural competences in teacher preparation programs and through professional development: A review. In *Teaching and Teacher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103236>

Rubiono, G., & Finahari, N. (2017). Dosen: Profil-profil Sederhana dalam Profesi yang Rumit. *JAS-PT Jurnal Analisis Sistem Pendidikan Tinggi*. <https://doi.org/10.36339/jaspt.v1i1.35>

Rudolph, C. W., Zacher, H., & Hirschi, A. (2019). Empirical Developments in Career Construction Theory.

- Journal of Vocational Behavior, 111(xxxx), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2018.12.003>
- Santos, G. G. (2016). Career barriers influencing career success: A focus on academics' perceptions and experiences. *Career Development International*, 21(1), 60–84.
- Savickas, M. L. (2005). The Theory and Practise of Career Construction. In S.D.Brown & R.W.Lent, *Career Development and Counseling: Putting Theory and Research to Work*. In Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.112.483.211-a>
- Savickas, M. L. (2013). Career Construction Theory and Practice. In S.D.Brown & R.W.Lent, *Career Development and Counseling: Putting Theory and Research to Work*. In Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Savickas, M. L. (2016). Reflection and Reflexivity During Life-Design Interventions: Comments on Career Construction Counseling. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 97, 84–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2016.09.001>
- Seggelen, I. van, & Dam, D. K. van. (2016). Self-reflection as a mediator between self-efficacy and well-being. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 31(1), 18–33.
- Son, S. J. (2018). The more reflective, the more career-adaptable: A two-wave mediation and moderation analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 109, 44–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2018.09.004>
- Sprott, R. A. (2019). Factors that Foster and Deter Advanced Teachers' Professional Development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 77, 321–331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.11.001>
- Sutherland, K. A. (2017). Constructions of Success in Academia: An Early Career Perspective. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(4), 743–759. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2015.1072150>
- Tharmaseelan, N., Inkson, K., & Carr, S. C. (2010). Migration and career success: testing a time-sequenced model. *Career Development International*, 15(3), 218–238.
- Tokar, D. M., Savickas, M. L., & Kaut, K. P. (2019). A Test of the Career Construction Theory Model of Adaptation in Adult Workers With Chiari Malformation. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 106907271986773. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1069072719867733>
- Xie, B., Xia, M., Xin, X., & Zhou, W. (2016). Linking Calling to Work Engagement and Subjective Career Success: The Perspective of Career Construction Theory. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 94, 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2016.02.011>
- Yun, M. R., Shin, N., Kim, H., Jang, I. S., Ha, M. J., & Yu, B. (2020). Effects of School-Based Meditation Courses on Self-Reflection, Academic Attention, and Subjective Well-Being in South Korean Middle School Students. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing*, 54(xxxx), e61–e68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedn.2020.05.002>
- Zamir, S. (2018). A Teaching Career: Mobility and Stagnation. *Athens Journal of Education*, 5(2), 145–160. <https://doi.org/10.30958/aje.5-2-3>
- Ziedonis, D., & Ahn, M. S. (2019). Professional Development for Clinical Faculty in Academia: Focus on Teaching, Research, and Leadership. *Psychiatric Clinics of North America*, 42(3), 389–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psc.2019.05.009>